

1 **Long-term shift towards shady and nutrient-rich habitats in Central**
2 **European temperate forests**

3

4 Ondřej Vild^{1,*}, Markéta Chudomelová¹, Martin Macek¹, Martin Kopecký^{1,2}, Jindřich Prach^{3,4}, Petr
5 Petřík^{1,8}, Petr Halas⁵, Michal Juříček⁶, Marie Smyčková^{2,3}, Jan Šebesta⁷, Martin Vojík⁸ & Radim
6 Hédl^{1,9}

7

8 ¹ Institute of Botany of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Zámek 1, 252 43 Průhonice, Czech
9 Republic;

10 ² Department of Forest Ecology, Faculty of Forestry and Wood Sciences, Czech University of
11 Life Sciences Prague, Kamýcká 129, 165 00 Praha 6, Czech Republic;

12 ³ Department of Botany, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Benátská 2, 128 00 Prague 2,
13 Czech Republic;

14 ⁴ Center for Theoretical Study, Charles University and the Czech Academy of Sciences, Jilská 1,
15 11 000 Prague 1, Czech Republic;

16 ⁵ The Czech Academy of Sciences, Institute of Geonics, Studentská 1768, 708 00 Ostrava-
17 Poruba, Czech Republic;

18 ⁶ Kunice 94, 679 71, Czech Republic;

19 ⁷ Department of Forest Botany, Dendrology and Geobiocoenology, Faculty of Forestry and
20 Wood Technology, Mendel University, Zemědělská 3, 613 00, Brno, Czech Republic;

21 ⁸ Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Kamýcká 129,
22 165 21 Prague 6, Czech Republic;

23 ⁹ Department of Botany, Palacký University in Olomouc, Šlechtitelů 27, 783 71 Olomouc, Czech
24 Republic

25

26 * corresponding author; full postal address:

27 Institute of Botany of the CAS

28 Department of Vegetation Ecology

29 Lidická 25/27

30 602 00 Brno

31 Czech Republic

32 E-mail addresses: O. Vild: ondrej.vild@ibot.cas.cz, tel.: +420 541 126 218; fax: +420 541 126

33 234; M. Chudomelová: marketa.chudomelova@ibot.cas.cz; M. Macek:

34 martin.macek@ibot.cas.cz; M. Kopecký: ma.kopecky@gmail.com; J. Prach:

35 jindrprach@gmail.com; P. Petřík: petr.petrik@ibot.cas.cz; P. Halas: petrhalas.cz@gmail.com,

36 M. Juříček: michal.jumi.juricek@gmail.com; M. Smyčková: smyckova@fld.czu.cz; J. Šebesta:

37 jan.sebesta@mendelu.cz; M. Vojík: vojik@fzp.czu.cz; R. Hédli: radim.hedl@ibot.cas.cz

38 ORCIDs: Ondřej Vild: 0000-0002-0728-2392, Markéta Chudomelová: 0000-0001-7845-4000,

39 Martin Macek: 0000-0002-5609-5921, Martin Kopecký: 0000-0002-1018-9316, Jindřich Prach:

40 0000-0002-7628-6020, Petr Petřík: 0000-0001-8518-6737, Marie Smyčková: 0000-0003-2306-

41 9409, Jan Šebesta: 0000-0003-2891-2346, Martin Vojík: 0000-0001-9735-5120, Radim Hédli:

42 0000-0002-6040-8126.

43

Total word count (excluding summary, references, and legends)	4545
Summary	198
Introduction	706
Materials and Methods	1372
Results	637
Discussion	1830
Acknowledgements	137
No. of Figures	5
No. of Tables	1
No. of Supporting Information files (Fig. S1; Table S1-S3)	4

44

45 Keywords: biodiversity, global change, long-term change, plant community, vegetation resurvey,
 46 forest succession, forest understory

47 Nomenclature: Danihelka et al. (2012)

48 **Summary**

- 49 ● Biodiversity worldwide has been under increasing anthropogenic pressure in the past
50 century. The long-term response of biotic communities has been tackled primarily by
51 focusing on species richness, community composition and functionality. Equally
52 important are shifts between entire communities and habitat types, which remain an
53 unexplored level of biodiversity change.
- 54 ● We have resurveyed more than 2,000 vegetation plots in temperate forests in central
55 Europe to capture changes over an average of five decades. The plots were assigned to
56 eight broad forest habitat types using an algorithmic classification system. We analysed
57 transitions between the habitat types and interpreted the trend in terms of changes in
58 environmental conditions.
- 59 ● We identified a directional shift along the combined gradients of canopy openness and
60 soil nutrients. Nutrient-poor open-canopy forest habitats have declined strongly in favour
61 of fertile closed-canopy habitats. However, the shift was not uniform across the whole
62 gradients.
- 63 ● We conclude that the shifts in habitat types represent a century-long successional trend
64 with significant consequences for forest biodiversity. Open forest habitats should be
65 urgently targeted for plant diversity restoration through implementation of active
66 management. The approach presented here can be applied to other habitat types and at
67 different spatio-temporal scales.

68 1. Introduction

69 The world's ecosystems are experiencing unprecedented changes in biodiversity. These are
70 observed not only as species losses (Pimm et al., 1995) but also as changes in community
71 composition (Dornelas et al., 2014). The main drivers of these changes are habitat loss,
72 overexploitation, invasive species, climate change and pollution (Pereira, Navarro, & Martins,
73 2012). These drivers affect most taxonomic groups, including amphibians, insects and vascular
74 plants (Dornelas et al., 2014; Hoffmann et al., 2010; Outhwaite, McCann, & Newbold, 2022).

75 In temperate forests, studies of long-term changes in plant communities have revealed
76 biotic homogenisation and an increase in nutrient-demanding species (Hédli et al., 2010;
77 Verheyen et al., 2012; Prausová et al., 2020). However, the magnitude of changes differ in
78 individual sites. Some studies have found that nutrient-poor sites experience greater
79 compositional changes compared to mesophilous or nutrient-rich sites (Heinrichs & Schmidt,
80 2016; Dittmann et al., 2018). This variability underscores the importance of long-term resurveys
81 covering broad community and environmental gradients. Such studies can help determine how
82 different factors, including climate and soil conditions, impact anthropogenic biodiversity
83 changes (Perring et al., 2018a; Vandvik et al., 2020; Lynn et al., 2021).

84 The main drivers of understorey changes in temperate forest communities include nitrogen
85 deposition, forest management and large herbivores (Bernhardt-Römermann et al., 2015).
86 However, none of the many factors driving ecosystem dynamics act independently, but rather in
87 mutual and often complex interactions (Tylianakis et al., 2008; Perring et al., 2018a; for contrary
88 evidence see Koerner et al., 2023). Several studies have investigated the spatial variability of
89 understorey changes in the context of the interaction between nitrogen deposition and other
90 factors. Nitrogen deposition was found to have a greater effect on species composition on
91 oligotrophic sites than on sites with higher fertility (Ewald et al., 2013; Roth et al., 2021).

92 Historical context of management also plays a role, where a decrease in understorey species
93 richness was observed on sites with former coppice management, while the opposite was found
94 in forests historically managed as high forests (Perring et al., 2018b).

95 Differences in the sensitivity of forest habitats to global change drivers have conservation
96 implications. While climate change-induced drought is the main threat to beech forests in
97 Europe (Martinez et al., 2022), oak and other open forest habitats are mostly threatened by the
98 abandonment of traditional coppice management combined with atmospheric nitrogen
99 deposition (Chudomelová et al., 2017). Effective conservation of forest habitats therefore
100 requires tailored strategies, in which a detailed understanding of habitat-specific vulnerabilities
101 becomes crucial.

102 In order to understand long-term biodiversity changes on the level of biotic communities,
103 most assessments focus on species richness (Vellend et al., 2013; Dornelas et al., 2014), more
104 recently also including relative species abundance (Jandt et al., 2022). Recent critical
105 assessment of the reliability of time series data, have shown that estimates of species richness
106 change are sensitive to the combination of data sets of different origins, which can lead to
107 erroneous results (Douda et al., 2023; Valdez et al., 2023). Compared to conventional
108 approaches to assessing biodiversity change, here we bring a new perspective based on the
109 classification of vegetation types according to their characteristic species composition. We
110 analyse qualitative changes in plant biodiversity by taking into account changes in the
111 assignment of samples to individual habitat types. This approach builds on a robust and widely
112 used system of vegetation classification developed over the past century (Mucina et al., 2016).
113 An elaborate system for classifying vegetation into hierarchically arranged types provides an
114 excellent framework for understanding changes in plant biodiversity. In addition to its scientific
115 importance, this approach also has practical applications as the habitat level is often used as a
116 framework in conservation policy and decision-making. In particular, the system of natural

117 habitats that forms the backbone of the EU's Natura 2000 framework (Habitats Directive)
118 directly follows the vegetation classification approach (Loidi, 1999; Evans, 2006).

119 We used a large, original, nationwide dataset of forest vegetation plots resurveyed on
120 average after five decades. The plots represent a wide range of environmental conditions and
121 forest types. We aimed to test our hypothesis that there was a long-term trend detectable as
122 shifts between forest habitats. Based on evidence from existing studies in temperate
123 ecosystems, we predicted that this trend reflects a succession towards more fertile and shady
124 habitats.

125 **2. Materials and Methods**

126 **2.1 Data source**

127 We resurveyed 2,292 vegetation plots in temperate forests in the Czech Republic. The plots
128 cover a wide range of climatic and substrate gradients in the region. They are situated at
129 elevations ranging from 145 m to 1250 m a.s.l. with a median of 399 m. The size of most plots is
130 400 or 500 m², which allows for a standardized record of the local diversity of the plant
131 communities studied (Fig. S1). The plots are located mainly in ancient forests, which have had
132 continuity of forest land-use since at least the mid-19th century (Hermy, 1999). However, nearly
133 all the plots have been and still are influenced by human activities of various intensities. This
134 also applies to nature reserves with former traditional management (often coppicing) and
135 commercial forests with a rotation period of at least 80 years or longer. The forests surveyed
136 mostly represent natural to semi-natural vegetation. Clearings and young stands were not
137 included.

138 Two sampling surveys of each plot were conducted to study the composition and structure
139 of the plant community. The first sampling (baseline survey) took place mainly in the 1950s to
140 1970s (Fig. S1). The datasets included various sources and authors, but by far the largest
141 source are the standardized forest typology monitoring plots carried out by today's Forest
142 Management Institute (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic). The second sampling
143 (resurvey) was carried out mostly by the authors of this study between 2002 and 2018. The
144 average interval between the two surveys was 52 years, mostly 45 to 60 years. For the
145 resurvey, plots were relocated using a combination of information from contemporary maps, site
146 descriptions with local topography, tree species composition, and occasionally the remains of
147 soil sampling pits or paint markings on trees. The plots are therefore typically quasi (or semi)-
148 permanent (Kapfer et al., 2017). This approach is relatively robust in terms of locating historical
149 vegetation plots (Kopecký & Macek, 2015; but see Verheyen et al., 2018). All vascular plant
150 species were recorded with an estimate of cover/abundance in each plot. Zlatník scale (Zlatník,
151 1953) was used for this estimation in the baseline survey and a similar Braun-Blanquet scale
152 (Westhoff & van der Maarel, 1978) was used in the resurvey. Stand age was not recorded,
153 therefore a systematic change in stand age between the sampling periods cannot be ruled out.

154 **2.2 Data analyses**

155 Samples of plant communities from the historical survey and the resurvey were assigned to
156 predefined vegetation types. In the first step, an automated algorithm developed for the Czech
157 national vegetation survey was used (Chytrý & Tichý, 2018; Chytrý et al., 2020a). All samples
158 were classified into basic-level vegetation types, called associations (Chytrý, 2013). The
159 classification is defined by the combination of diagnostic species groups, and sometimes by the
160 dominance of a single species. Species groups include three or more species that are
161 diagnostic for a particular vegetation association (see example in Methods S1). The proportion

162 of directly classified samples that met the predefined criteria was similar in both the baseline
163 and resurvey, totalling 609 (26.2%) and 571 (24.9%) samples, respectively. In the second step,
164 all unclassified samples were assigned to vegetation types by calculating their compositional
165 similarity to the already classified samples using the Frequency-Positive Fidelity Index (FPFI;
166 Tichý, 2005; Chytrý et al., 2020a).

167 The classification yielded 45 vegetation associations. Due to the hierarchical nature of the
168 classification system, the next highest category, vegetation alliance, was used (Table 1). The
169 resulting 15 alliances are directly compatible with the European EUNIS Habitat Classification
170 (Chytrý et al., 2020b). Alliances with less than 60 samples and non-forest vegetation were
171 merged into a single group (Table S1). Three thermophilous oak forest alliances were also
172 merged into one group. The final dataset includes eight groups, representing the main forest
173 habitat types in the region (Table 1). All analyses were performed using Juice software, ver. 7.1
174 (Tichý, 2002).

175 To assess the nature of habitat change, we used six complementary approaches:

- 176 1. The number of samples classified to individual habitats was compared between the
177 baseline and resurvey to evaluate changes in the representation of habitat types. Habitat
178 stability was estimated based on the proportion of samples with unchanged
179 classification. Increase or decrease was calculated separately for each habitat type as
180 the proportion of samples classified as a different habitat in the resurvey compared to its
181 counterpart in the baseline survey and tested for significance by McNemar's Chi-squared
182 test.
- 183 2. To visualise changes in plot classification over time, a chord diagram was constructed
184 using the R *chorddiag* package (Flor, 2019). Only actual transitions were considered,

185 and the proportions of transitions for each habitat were standardised to account for
186 differences in their frequency.

187 3. To evaluate the change in the habitat distinctiveness, we used the list of diagnostic
188 species for each corresponding vegetation alliance from Chytrý & Tichý (2003). For
189 thermophilous oak forests, we selected diagnostic species from all three corresponding
190 alliances. For each sample, we recorded the presence of all diagnostic species
191 associated with each habitat type, regardless of sample classification. We then
192 calculated the proportion of diagnostic species relative to all species in each sample and
193 compared between the two surveys using a two-sample Wilcoxon test with Bonferroni
194 adjustment.

195 4. Habitat similarities in species composition and individual temporal changes were
196 illustrated by Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS). A matrix of Bray–Curtis
197 dissimilarities was used, with cover data square-root transformed and standardized
198 using Wisconsin double standardisation. To maximise variance along the first ordination
199 axis, principal component analysis was used to centre and rotate the two-dimensional
200 configuration with the lowest stress after 1000 random starts. To assess whether the
201 change in NMDS scores along the first and second NMDS axes was significant, we
202 compared plot positions in the baseline and resurvey using the paired Approximative
203 two-sample Fisher-Pitman permutation test with 99,999 permutations. The calculations
204 were done using the *metaMDS* function from the *vegan* package (Oksanen et al., 2020)
205 and the *oneway_test* function from the *coin* package (Hothorn et al., 2006) in R, ver.
206 4.3.0 (R Core Team, 2023).

207 5. To explore if there was a shift from nutrient-poor and open habitats to fertile and shady
208 habitats, ecological gradients of light availability and soil nutrients were approximated
209 using Ellenberg indicator values (EIV; Ellenberg & Leuschner, 2010). Unweighted means
210 calculated for samples from species values were passively fitted to ordination space as a

211 smooth surface through the *ordisurf* function from the *vegan* package. We used the EIVs
 212 only to facilitate ecological interpretations, as changes in EIVs are not suitable to be
 213 used as predictors of compositional changes.

214 6. To assess the role of overstorey in the changes, we calculated differences in relative plot
 215 cover of eleven tree taxa dominant in the particular habitats between the resurvey and
 216 baseline pairs considering cover estimates (%). Plot pairs where a particular taxon was
 217 absent were excluded. The same statistical testing and visualisation as for the diagnostic
 218 species were used.

219 Table 1: Forest habitat types used to assess long-term shifts in the biodiversity of forest plant
 220 communities. The number of samples assigned to each habitat in the baseline and resurvey is
 221 given, totalling 2,292 plots.

Forest habitat type	Number of samples		Short description
	Baseline	Resurvey	
Acidophilous pine forests	100	74	Lowland open-canopy forests on extremely nutrient-poor, acidic soils of sandy and rocky substrates; dominated by <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> .
Acidophilous oak forests	358	251	Lowland open-canopy forests on acidic, nutrient-poor soils; dominated by <i>Quercus</i> spp.
Thermophilous oak forests	118	76	Lowland open-canopy forests on various types of well-drained substrates; dominated by <i>Quercus</i> spp.
Oak-hornbeam forests	447	326	Lowland semi-open to closed-canopy forests on mesic soils; dominated by <i>Carpinus betulus</i> and <i>Quercus</i> spp.
Ash-alder alluvial forests	102	168	Lowland to mountain semi-open to closed-canopy forests on moist to wet, nutrient-rich soils; dominated by <i>Alnus</i> spp., <i>Fraxinus</i> spp. and <i>Quercus</i> spp.
Ravine forests	100	130	Usually on steep slopes, most commonly in deep river valleys; dominated by <i>Acer</i> spp., <i>Fraxinus</i> spp., <i>Tilia</i> spp. and <i>Ulmus glabra</i> .
Eutrophic beech forests	271	355	Upland to mountain closed-canopy forests on well-drained, relatively nutrient-rich soils; dominated by <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> .

Acidophilous beech forests	549	633	Upland to mountain closed-canopy forests on acidic, well-drained, nutrient-poor soils; dominated by <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> .
Other vegetation types	247	279	Mixed category with different types of communities including spruce forests and non-forest vegetation.

222

223 3. Results

224 The habitat type has changed in 42% of the plots, with large variation between the habitats (Fig.
 225 1). The greatest loss was in the two habitats of Oak-hornbeam and Acidophilous oak forests,
 226 where only 21% and 24% of the plots, respectively, retained their original classification. In
 227 contrast, the most stable habitats were Ash-alder alluvial forest and Ravine forest, where 89%
 228 and 71% of plots, respectively, remained in the same group. A complementary pattern was
 229 found in the proportion of plots gained by the habitats. Expressed as the number of plots gained
 230 in relation to the number of plots in the baseline survey, the largest gains were recorded in Ash-
 231 alder alluvial forests (75%) and Eutrophic beech forests (74%), while the opposite was true for
 232 Thermophilous oak forests (26%) and Acidophilous pine forests (42%). As a result, the highest
 233 net relative gain was observed for Ash-alder alluvial forests (+65%) followed by Acidophilous
 234 beech forests (+31%) and Ravine forests (+30%). The largest net relative declines were
 235 observed for Thermophilous oak forests (-36%), Oak-hornbeam forests (-27%) and
 236 Acidophilous pine forests (-26%). All the changes were statistically significant, except for the
 237 mixed group.

238 Fig. 1: Stability and change of forest habitats expressed as changes in plot classification
 239 between the two surveys. The red bars represent the proportion of plots classified in a different
 240 class in the resurvey, while the green bars represent the proportion of plots newly classified in
 241 that habitat type compared to the baseline survey. Percentages on the right indicate the net
 242 loss/gain of plots in particular habitats. Open-canopy forest habitats (four top ones) show lower
 243 stability and gains, while closed-canopy forest habitats (five bottom ones) show higher stability
 244 and gains.

245 An analysis of individual-sample transitions between the forest habitats is presented in Fig. 2.
 246 Note that the order of habitats in the diagram follows a clockwise gradient of environmental
 247 conditions – see below. The analysis revealed a general pattern of shift from open-canopy oak
 248 and pine forests (left, warm colours) towards shady forests dominated by beech and other
 249 broadleaved species (right, cold colours).

250

251 Fig. 2: The chord diagram shows shifts of 961 individual plots between the baseline survey and
 252 the resurvey based on the classification into forest habitat. Plots that remained unchanged in
 253 classification are not shown. To standardize changes across the habitats, the width of each
 254 compartment was set to the same size, irrespective of the number of plots.

255
 256

257 The decline in the abundance of diagnostic species indicates a decrease in the compositional
 258 distinctiveness of the four open-canopy forest habitats (Fig. 3). In contrast, the diagnostic
 259 species of the closed-canopy habitats remained relatively stable or even increased.

260 Fig. 3: Shift in floristic distinctiveness of eight forest habitats, measured as change in proportion
 261 of diagnostic species between baseline and resurvey samples. Fills indicate significant ($P <$
 262 0.05) increases (green) or decreases (pink). Boxplots show medians as thick lines and mean as
 263 points, 25–75% percentiles, 1.5 interquartile ranges and outliers.

264
 265

266 The NMDS ordination shows the position of the eight habitats along two main environmental
 267 gradients (Fig. 4). As indicated by the EIVs for light and nutrients, the primary gradient reflects
 268 soil nutrients, while the second gradient corresponds to light availability, which can be
 269 interpreted as canopy openness. The four semi-open to closed-canopy habitats are situated in
 270 the upper part of the diagram, whereas the three open-canopy habitats are in the lower half of
 271 the diagram, with the oak-hornbeam habitats in an intermediate position. The soil nutrient

272 gradient runs partially across the light availability gradient, with acidophilous forest communities
273 of nutrient-poor substrates at the right end gradually transitioning to nutrient-demanding
274 communities often on relatively base-rich soils at the left end.

275 While the shift along the first NMDS axis was not significant ($Z = -1.575$, $p = 0.115$), there
276 was a significant shift along the second axis ($Z = 9.0407$, $p < 0.001$). The results indicate a clear
277 change in species composition towards communities with more nutrient-demanding and shade-
278 tolerant species (Fig. 4; Fig S2). This trend is not equally strong across the habitats. It is most
279 pronounced in habitats characterized by open-canopy and low soil nutrients, i.e. Thermophilous
280 and Acidophilous oak forests, and Acidophilous pine forests. In contrast, closed-canopy forests,
281 including Ash-alder alluvial forests, Ravine forests, and Eutrophic and Acidophilous beech
282 forests, are relatively stable in terms of change along these gradients.

283
284 Fig. 4: Non-metric multidimensional scaling diagram showing temporal shifts in different habitat
285 types due to changes in species composition. Points show centroid positions from the baseline
286 (solid circles) and resurvey (open circles) samples grouped by their baseline habitat type. The
287 largest shifts were observed in open-canopy habitats dominated by oak and pine, where
288 species composition shifted markedly toward more shade-tolerant and nutrient-demanding

289 species. In contrast, closed-canopy beech forest or alluvial forest habitats experienced relatively
290 little change. The main environmental gradients of soil nutrients and light availability, as
291 indicated by plant community composition, are outlined in the two side diagrams, which show
292 the projected isolines of mean Ellenberg indicator values. The nutrient gradient runs along the
293 first axis in acidophilous habitats and along the second axis in other habitats, from nutrient-poor
294 soils (EIVs for nutrients 2 to 4) to relatively nutrient-rich soils (>6). The light gradient, with an
295 opposite pattern along the axes to the nutrient gradient, ranges from shady (EIV for light <4) to
296 open-canopy forests (>6).

297 Changes in the relative plot cover of the main tree species (Fig. 5) corroborate the patterns
298 identified by the analysis of habitat shifts. Trees that are dominant in declining habitats have
299 decreased in cover (*Pinus sylvestris* and *Quercus* spp.). On the other hand, there was an
300 increase in the cover of trees found in habitats that are increasing (*Fraxinus* spp., *Acer* spp.,
301 *Tilia* spp. and *Fagus sylvatica*). A decrease in two common conifer species (*Abies alba* and
302 *Picea abies*) indicates other processes in addition to the main successional shift.

303

305 Fig. 5: Change in relative plot cover of the main tree taxa between baseline and resurvey plots.
 306 Shading indicates significant ($P < 0.05$) increases (green) or decreases (pink). Boxplots show
 307 medians as thick lines and means as points, 25–75% percentiles, 1.5 interquartile ranges and
 308 outliers.

309 4. Discussion

310 4.1 Dark or open forests?

311 We found that the long-term directional changes in the biodiversity of temperate forest
312 communities in Europe can be observed at the level of habitat types. Using over 2,000
313 resurveyed forest plots, we observed a strong decline in oligotrophic open-canopy habitats and
314 an increase in nutrient-rich closed-canopy forest habitats. This pattern paints a consistent
315 picture of a successional shift among the eight broadly defined forest habitat types. However,
316 the succession towards darker and more fertile forests was remarkably more pronounced in
317 habitats with low soil fertility and open canopies. The ecological succession and associated
318 decline of communities with light-demanding and oligotrophic plant species are in line with
319 conclusions from other large-scale studies across various ecosystems (Tape et al., 2006;
320 Verheyen et al., 2012; Dengler et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2015).

321 Furthermore, the interpretation presented here provides an alternative perspective to the
322 widely accepted 'forest microclimate buffering' hypothesis claiming that shady forests are the
323 key to protecting forest plant biodiversity (De Frenne et al., 2013; Zellweger et al., 2020). Our
324 results point to an adverse aspect of increasing shade levels, namely a decline in biodiversity in
325 formerly widespread open forest habitats. Our comparison across a wide range of forest
326 habitats and a long gradient of environmental conditions shows that shady forests are not the
327 desired solution for biodiversity conservation, at least for plant communities. These habitats may
328 be more resilient to climate change than the open-canopy forests, but the no less important
329 value of open forests is their biodiversity, consisting of a wide range of species, including those
330 from non-forest habitats (Roleček et al., 2017).

331 In central Europe, beech forests are generally considered to be at low risk, while most pine-
332 and oak-dominated forest types in the region are red-listed (Chytrý et al., 2019). Our results are
333 in line with these findings and existing scientific consensus that oligotrophic open forest habitats
334 are among the most threatened ecosystems in Europe and are rapidly declining globally
335 (Chudomelová et al., 2017; Knott et al., 2019; Alexander et al., 2021). The decline is due to

336 management changes and sometimes drought-induced shifts in dominant tree species
337 (Pederson et al. 2015, Rigling et al., 2013). We argue that while protecting dark forest
338 environment may be valuable in some cases, maintaining an open-canopy environment should
339 be a priority in other habitats where biodiversity is of concern. The main challenge for
340 biodiversity management is therefore to find ways of maintaining forests with open canopies and
341 rich understories in the face of a changing environment. To do this, we need to understand the
342 complex relationships between species richness and the availability of light and nutrients in a
343 changing environment.

344 **4.2 The puzzle of interacting factors**

345 While we have clearly shown that open and nutrient-poor forest habitats and their understories
346 are changing more rapidly in response to changing conditions compared to closed and nutrient-
347 rich forests, the distinction between the two is far from straightforward. Previous studies in
348 broadleaved forests have shown that sites with higher levels of light availability tend to
349 experience more pronounced species turnover and a decrease in species richness over time
350 (Verheyen et al., 2012; Bernhardt-Römermann et al., 2015). This observation can be explained
351 by the gradual closure of the forest canopy, resulting in the displacement of light-demanding
352 species. On the other hand, this is not as strong in areas with already closed canopies. This
353 process has also been observed in eastern North America, where fire suppression has led to
354 the replacement of oak and pine forests by maple forests (Rogers et al., 2008; Nowacki &
355 Abrams, 2015). In European studies, forests with light-demanding species experienced an
356 increase in shade-tolerant species, and vice versa, leading to a process of biotic
357 homogenisation (Kopecký et al. 2013; Chudomelová et al., 2017; Perring et al., 2018b, Prach &
358 Kopecký 2018). Our study corroborates the above findings by showing that the formerly open-
359 canopy oak and pine forest habitats and their light-demanding understorey communities have

360 largely shifted towards closed-canopy forest types and have undergone a process of
361 compositional homogenisation.

362 In addition to light conditions, site fertility is another key factor driving transitions between
363 forest habitats. Previous research by Perring et al. (2018a) showed that across much of the
364 nitrogen deposition gradient in Europe, species composition shifted in favour of light-demanding
365 species on sites with nutrient-poor soils, while the opposite trend occurred on sites with nutrient-
366 rich soils. Our results appear to contradict this pattern, as declining oak and pine habitats
367 generally occur on relatively poor soils. Perring et al. (2018a) observed that this pattern can be
368 reversed on sites with lower levels of N-deposition, but this does not explain the pattern
369 observed in our study, as the sites are more in the middle of the European N-deposition
370 spectrum. It appears that initial light conditions were more important than soil fertility in
371 determining the changes in our open-canopy habitats characterised by both light-demanding
372 and oligotrophic species. This may be because the above study had a higher representation of
373 lowland forests with shade-tolerant flora, which are more common in oceanic regions of Europe.

374 The impact of soil fertility on understorey changes related to nutrient requirements was also
375 investigated in a large-scale study of over 100,000 forest vegetation plots in Europe (Ewald et
376 al. 2013). This study found that stands with initially low levels of nutrients, such as those
377 dominated by pine and oak, experienced a relatively greater increase in nitrogen than initially
378 more fertile stands, including those dominated by beech and alder. These findings are
379 consistent with our results and several smaller-scale long-term studies (Heinrichs & Schmidt,
380 2016; Dittmann et al., 2018; Prausová et al., 2020; Roth et al., 2022). Ewald et al. (2013)
381 suggested that one of the main reasons for the contrasting patterns in soils with different trophic
382 levels may be the recovery from long-term traditional management practices such as litter
383 raking, grazing, and coppicing.

384

385 **4.3 Management and conservation implications**

386 Other studies have shown that the transition from coppice to high forest management is a major
387 factor in the changes observed in forest understories (Brunet et al., 1996; Van Calster et al.,
388 2007; Hédli et al., 2010). This is because resprouting capacity, and hence coppice potential, is
389 highly variable between tree species: oak, lime and hornbeam are better at resprouting than
390 beech or conifers (Buckley & Mills, 2015). In forests managed as coppice-with-standards, the
391 coppiced underwood was historically composed of oak, hornbeam, lime, birch, or poplar,
392 whereas the standards of oak, beech and conifers formed the overstorey (Szabó et al., 2021).

393 Other common traditional management types include animal grazing and litter raking (Bürgi
394 et al., 2013). These practices involved the removal of large amounts of biomass and frequent
395 canopy disturbance, leading to a nutrient uptake from soils and the creation of relatively open-
396 canopy forests (Glatzel, 1991).

397 Paleoecological studies suggest that open forests, such as oak and pine forests, only
398 persisted throughout the Holocene in central Europe due to human influence (Jamrichová et al.,
399 2013; Kuneš et al., 2015). Therefore, the decline of plant species in open oligotrophic oakwoods
400 may be exacerbated by succession from historically relatively intensively managed forests to
401 modern long-rotation forests (Ewald et al., 2013; Chudomelová et al., 2017). Human impact at
402 higher elevations (>500 m a.s.l.) has historically been lower in Europe (Fuller et al., 1998; Kolář
403 et al., 2018), but in terms of vegetation change over the last century, the picture is generally
404 similar to that of lowland forests (Prach & Kopecký, 2018).

405 Management changes may have led not only to the decrease in light-demanding species
406 but also to the increase in nutrient-demanding species (Máliš et al., 2021). Verheyen et al.
407 (2012) found a negative correlation between changes in the frequency of nutrient-demanding
408 and light-demanding species. This suggests that canopy closure and related factors, rather than

409 N deposition itself, may be the major driver of long-term changes common to temperate
410 understories.

411 Contrasting environmental and historical factors are clearly responsible for the distinct
412 responses of different forest habitats. As a result, each habitat type faces specific threats
413 resulting in shifts from one habitat to another. This has important implications for conservation
414 and restoration management. Our study helped to identify changes in different forest habitats,
415 which can help to select appropriate conservation measures. Therefore, conservation of open
416 and nutrient-poor forests should include appropriate forms of active management, such as
417 coppicing, litter raking or grazing, to ensure their long-term survival (Kirby & Watkins, 2015).

418 **4.4 Focus on habitat types and conclusions**

419 We have shown that the classification of plant communities into habitat types provides valuable
420 insights into long-term biodiversity changes. In contrast to the prevailing focus on species
421 richness in biodiversity change assessment, our approach has the advantage that it does not
422 explicitly use the number of species. This effectively overcomes the 'biodiversity conservation
423 paradox', or the average net zero change in species diversity (Vellend, 2017; Jandt et al., 2022).
424 As recently shown by Valdez et al. (2023), repeated local-scale community records based on
425 species richness are likely to be burdened with uncontrollable errors when attempting to detect
426 biodiversity trends at larger spatial and temporal scales. Here, we present a qualitatively
427 different approach that is independent of species richness. It considers a high level of
428 biodiversity organisation, the community and habitat types, that has been almost completely
429 neglected in global change research. Moreover, this approach has an important link to nature
430 conservation policy at the European Union level, as the conceptually and factually identical way
431 of defining habitat types forms the basis for the protection of natural habitat types under the
432 Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC (Natura 2000).

433 A distinctive feature of forest plant communities is vertical layering. In European temperate
434 forests, the canopy tends to be species-poor, often dominated by a single species. The
435 understorey can consist of hundreds of different species of herbs. The basic feature of our
436 classification method is that it considers both the tree overstorey and the herbaceous
437 understorey. A key element is groups of co-occurring diagnostic herb species and their specific
438 combinations that define individual communities (Chytrý et al., 2020a). In our classification
439 method, both understorey and overstorey were used together and we did not determine the
440 separate contributions of each layer to the classification. Although changes in the overstorey
441 may be the result of forest management decisions, we are not aware of significant management
442 transitions in most of our study sites, so tree composition has remained largely similar over time.

443 Future research could build on this approach to explore the role of different driving factors in
444 shaping forest biodiversity in different forest habitat types. Understanding these drivers is crucial
445 to inform effective conservation strategies that can mitigate the negative impacts of
446 anthropogenic pressures on forest ecosystems. Therefore, this study provides valuable insight
447 into the variability of vegetation responses by showing that the general shift from nutrient-poor
448 open forests to fertile and shady forests over the past five decades has not been uniform across
449 all forest types. Nutrient-poor and open habitats showed marked changes, while shady and
450 nutrient-rich forests have been more stable. The study's approach can be applied to other
451 habitat types and different spatio-temporal scales to better understand the impact of
452 anthropogenic pressures on ecosystems.

453

454 Acknowledgments

455 We would like to thank the Forest Management Institute (FMI) for the opportunity to use
456 extensive data of historical monitoring plots from the Forest Typology Database. In particular,
457 we thank Václav Zouhar and Tadeáš Štěřba of the FMI for their long-term cooperation. We
458 would also like to thank Jiří Vaniček, Alina Valentová and Daniel Volařík for their help in the
459 fieldwork.

460 This study was funded by the projects “Application of traditional knowledge to halt biodiversity
461 loss in woodlands” (TO01000132) by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic and
462 Norway Grants 2014–2021, “Centre for landscape and biodiversity” (SS02030018) by the
463 Technology Agency of the Czech Republic, project 21-11487S by the Czech
464 Science Foundation, postdoctoral fellowship L200052302 to MC, and the long-term research
465 development project RVO 67985939 to the Institute of Botany of the Czech Academy of
466 Sciences.

467 Competing interests

468 None declared.

469 Author contributions

470 RH, OV and MC planned and designed the research; all authors conducted fieldwork; OV and
471 MM analysed data; OV, RH and MC drafted the manuscript; all authors revised and edited the
472 manuscript.

473 Data availability

474 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author
475 upon reasonable request, except for the baseline data which are available on request from the
476 Forest Management Institute (FMI), Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic.

477 References

- 478 **Bernhardt-Römermann M, Baeten L, Craven D, De Frenne P, Hédli R, Lenoir J, Bert D,**
479 **Brunet J, Chudomelová M, Decocq G et al. 2015.** Drivers of temporal changes in
480 temperate forest plant diversity vary across spatial scales. *Global Change Biology* **21**(10):
481 3726–3737. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12993>
- 482 **Brunet J, Falkengren-Grerup U, Tyler G. 1996.** Herb layer vegetation of south Swedish beech
483 and oak forests—effects of management and soil acidity during one decade. *Forest*
484 *Ecology and Management* **88**(3): 259–272. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127\(96\)03845-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127(96)03845-5)
- 485 **Buckley P, Mills J. 2015.** The flora and fauna of coppice woods: winners and losers of active
486 management or neglect? In: Kirby KJ, Watkins C, eds. *Europe's changing woods and*
487 *forests: from wildwood to managed landscapes*. CABI, Wallingford, UK.
488 <https://doi.org/10.1079/9781780643373.0000>
- 489 **Bürgi M, Gimmi U, Stuber M. 2013.** Assessing traditional knowledge on forest uses to
490 understand forest ecosystem dynamics. *Forest Ecology and Management* **289**: 115–122.
491 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2012.10.012>

- 492 **Chudomelová M, Hédli R, Zouhar V, Szabó P. 2017.** Open oakwoods facing modern threats:
493 Will they survive the next fifty years? *Biological Conservation* **210**: 163–173.
494 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2017.04.017>
- 495 **Chytrý M (Ed.). 2013.** *Vegetation of the Czech Republic 4. Forest and scrub vegetation.*
496 Academia, Prague.
- 497 **Chytrý M, Hájek M, Kočí M, Pešout P, Roleček J, Sádlo J, Šumberová K, Sychra J,**
498 **Boublík K, Douda J et al. 2019.** Red list of habitats of the Czech Republic. *Ecological*
499 *Indicators* **106**: 105446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.105446>
- 500 **Chytrý M, Tichý L. 2003.** Diagnostic, constant and dominant species of vegetation classes and
501 alliances of the Czech Republic: a statistical revision. *Folia Facultatis Scientiarum*
502 *Naturalium Universitatis Masarykianae Brunensis* **108**: 1–231.
- 503 **Chytrý M, Tichý L. 2018.** National vegetation classification of the Czech Republic: A summary
504 of the approach. *Phytocoenologia* **48**(2): 121–131. <https://doi.org/10.1127/phyto/2017/0184>
- 505 **Chytrý M, Tichý L, Boublík K, Černý T, Douda J, Hájek M, Hájková P, Hédli R, Kočí M,**
506 **Krahulec F et al. 2020a.** CzechVeg-ESy: Expert system for automatic classification of
507 vegetation plots from the Czech Republic (v1-2020-01-12) [Data set]. Zenodo.
508 <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3605562>
- 509 **Chytrý M, Tichý L, Hennekens SM, Knollová I, Janssen JAM, Rodwell JS, Peterka T,**
510 **Marcenò C, Landucci F, Danihelka J et al. 2020b.** EUNIS Habitat Classification: expert
511 system, characteristic species combinations and distribution maps of European
512 habitats. *Applied Vegetation Science* **23**: 648–675. <https://doi.org/10.1111/avsc.12519>

- 513 **Danihelka J, Chrtek J, Kaplan Z. 2012.** Checklist of vascular plants of the Czech
514 Republic. *Preslia* **84**: 647–811. <https://doi.org/10.3897/phytokeys.9.2279>
- 515 **De Frenne P, Rodríguez-Sánchez F, Coomes DA, Baeten L, Verstraeten G, Vellend, M,**
516 **Bernhardt-Römermann, M, Brown, CD, Brunet, J, Cornelis et al. 2013.** Microclimate
517 moderates plant responses to macroclimate warming. *Proceedings of the National*
518 *Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **110**: 18561–18565.
519 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1311190110>
- 520 **Dengler J, Janišová M, Török P, Wellstein C. 2014.** Biodiversity of Palaeartic grasslands: A
521 synthesis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* **182**: 1–14.
522 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.12.015>
- 523 **Dittmann T, Heinken T, Schmidt M. 2018.** Die Wälder von Magdeburgerforst (Fläming,
524 Sachsen-Anhalt) – eine Wiederholungsuntersuchung nach sechs
525 Jahrzehnten. *Tuexenia* **38**: 11–42. <https://doi.org/10.14471/2018.38.009>
- 526 **Dornelas M, Gotelli NJ, McGill B, Shimadzu H, Moyes F et al. 2014.** Assemblage time series
527 reveal biodiversity change but not systematic loss. *Science* **344**: 296–299.
528 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1248484>
- 529 **Douda J, Doudová J, Holešťová A, Chudomelová M, Vild O, Boublík K, Černá M, Havrdová**
530 **A, Petřík P, Pychová N et al. 2023.** Historical sampling error: a neglected factor in long-
531 term biodiversity change research. *Biological Conservation* **286**(110317): 1–7.
532 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2023.110317>
- 533 **Ellenberg H, Leuschner C. 2010.** Zeigerwerte der Pflanzen Mitteleuropas. In: H.
534 Ellenberg & C. Leuschner (Eds.) *Vegetation Mitteleuropas mit den*, 6th edition. Ulmer,
535 Stuttgart. <https://doi.org/10.36198/9783825281045>

536 **Evans D. 2006.** The habitats of the European Union Habitats directive. *Biology and*
537 *Environment: Proceedings of the Royal Irish Academy* 106B: 167–173.

538 **Ewald J, Hennekens SM, Conrad S, Wohlgemuth T, Jansen F et al. 2013.** Spatial and
539 temporal patterns of Ellenberg nutrient values in forests of Germany and adjacent regions
540 – a survey based on phytosociological databases. *Tuexenia* **33**: 93–109.

541 **Flor M. 2019.** *chorddiag: Interactive chord diagrams*. R package version 0.1.2.
542 URL <https://github.com/mattflor/chorddiag/>

543 **Fuller JL, Foster DR, McLachlan JS, Drake N. 1998.** Impact of human activity on regional
544 forest composition and dynamics in Central New England. *Ecosystems* **1**:76–95.
545 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s100219900007>

546 **Glatzel G. 1991.** The impact of historic land use and modern forestry on nutrient relations of
547 Central European forest ecosystems. *Fertilizer Research*, **27**(1): 1–8.
548 <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01048603>

549 **Hanberry BB, Bragg DC, Alexander HD. 2020.** Open forest ecosystems: An excluded
550 state. *Forest Ecology and Management* **472**: 118256.
551 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2020.118256>

552 **Hédli R, Kopecký M, Komárek J. 2010.** Half a century of succession in a temperate oakwood:
553 from species-rich community to mesic forest. *Diversity and Distributions* **16**: 267–276.
554 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2010.00637.x>

555 **Heinrichs S, Schmidt W. 2016.** Biotic homogenization of herb layer composition between two
556 contrasting beech forest communities on limestone over 50 years. *Applied Vegetation*
557 *Science* **20**: 271–281. <https://doi.org/10.1111/avsc.12255>

- 558 **Hermý M. 1999.** An ecological comparison between ancient and other forest plant species of
559 Europe, and the implications for forest conservation. *Biological Conservation* **91**: 9–22
560 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207\(99\)00045-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207(99)00045-2)
- 561 **Hoffmann M, Hilton-Taylor C, Angulo A, Böhm M, Brooks TM, Butchart SHM, Carpenter**
562 **KE, Chanson J, Collen B, Cox NA et al. 2010.** The impact of conservation on the status
563 of the world's vertebrates. *Science* **330**: 1503–1509.
564 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1194442>
- 565 **Hothorn T, Hornik K, van de Wiel MA, Zeileis A. 2006.** A Lego system for conditional
566 inference. *The American Statistician* **60**(3): 257–263. doi:10.1198/000313006X118430.
- 567 **Jamrichová E, Szabó P, Hédl R, Kuneš P, Bobek P, Pelánková B. 2013.** Continuity and
568 change in the vegetation of a Central European oakwood. *The Holocene* **23**: 46–56.
569 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683612450200>
- 570 **Jandt U, Bruelheide H, Jansen F, Bonn A, Grescho V, Klenke RA, Sabatini FM, Bernhardt-**
571 **Römermann M, Blüml V, Dengler J et al. 2022.** More losses than gains during one
572 century of plant biodiversity change in Germany. *Nature* **611**: 512–518.
573 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05320-w>
- 574 **Kapfer J, Hédl R, Jurasinski G, Kopecký M, Schei FH, Grytnes JA. 2017.** Resurveying
575 historical vegetation data – opportunities and challenges. *Applied Vegetation Science* **20**:
576 164–171. <https://doi.org/10.1111/avsc.12269>
- 577 **Kirby KJ, Watkins C (eds). 2015.** *Europe's changing woods and forests: from wildwood to*
578 *managed landscapes*. CABI, UK. <https://doi.org/10.1079/9781780643373.0000>
- 579 **Knott JA, Desprez JM, Oswalt CM, Fei S. 2019.** Shifts in forest composition in the eastern
580 United States. *Forest Ecology and Management* **433**:176–183.
581 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2018.10.061>

582 **Koerner SE, Avolio ML, Blair JM, Knapp AK, Smith MD. 2023.** Multiple global change drivers
583 show independent, not interactive effects: a long-term case study in tallgrass prairie.
584 *Oecologia* **201**(1): 143-154. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-022-05295-5>

585 **Kopecký M, Hédli R, Szabó P. 2013.** Non-random extinctions dominate plant community
586 changes in abandoned coppices. *Journal of Applied Ecology* **50**:79–87.
587 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12010>

588 **Kopecký M, Macek M. 2015.** Vegetation resurvey is robust to plot location
589 uncertainty. *Diversity and Distributions* **21**:322–330. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12299>

590 **Kuneš P, Svobodová-Svitavská H, Kolář J, Hajnalová M, Abraham V, Macek M, Tkáč P,**
591 **Szabó P. 2015.** The origin of grasslands in the temperate forest zone of east-central
592 Europe: long-term legacy of climate and human impact. *Quaternary Science*
593 *Reviews* **116**:15–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2015.03.014>

594 **Loidi J. 1999.** Preserving biodiversity in the European Union: the Habitats Directive and its
595 application in Spain. *Plant Biosystems* **133**: 99-106.
596 <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263509909381538>

597 **Lynn JS, Klanderud K, Telford RJ, Goldberg DE, Vandvik V. 2021.** Macroecological context
598 predicts species' responses to climate warming. *Global Change Biology* **27**: 2088–2101.
599 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15532>

600 **Máliš F, Bobek P, Hédli R, Chudomelová M, Petřík P, Ujházy K, Ujházyová M, & Kopecký**
601 **M. 2021.** Historical charcoal burning and coppicing suppressed beech and increased forest
602 vegetation heterogeneity. *Journal of Vegetation Science* **32**(1): 1–14.
603 <https://doi.org/10.1111/jvs.12923>

604 **Martinez del Castillo E, Zang CS, Buras A, Hacket-Pain A, Esper J, Serrano-Notivoli R,**
605 **Hartl C, Weigel R, Klesse S, Resco de Dios V et al. 2022.** Climate-change-driven growth
606 decline of European beech forests. *Communications Biology* **5**: 163.
607 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-03107-3>

608 **Mucina L, Bültmann H, Dierßen K, Theurillat J-P, Raus T, Čarni A, Šumberová K, Willner**
609 **W, Dengler J, García RG et al. 2016.** Vegetation of Europe: hierarchical floristic
610 classification system of vascular plant, bryophyte, lichen, and algal communities. *Applied*
611 *Vegetation Science* **19**: 3–264. <https://doi.org/10.1111/AVSC.12257>

612 **Nowacki GJ, Abrams MD. 2015.** Is climate an important driver of post-European vegetation
613 change in the Eastern United States? *Global Change Biology* **21**(1): 314–334.
614 <https://doi.org/10.1111/GCB.12663>

615 **Oksanen J, Blanchet GF, Friendly M, Kindt R, Legendre P, McGlinn D, Minchin PR, O’Hara**
616 **RB, Simpson G, Solymos P et al. 2020.** *Vegan: Community ecology package. R package*
617 *version 2.5-7*. URL <http://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/vegan/vegan.pdf>

618 **Outhwaite CL, McCann P, Newbold T. 2022.** Agriculture and climate change are reshaping
619 insect biodiversity worldwide. *Nature* **605**(7908): 97–102. [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04644-x)
620 [022-04644-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04644-x)

621 **Pereira HM, Navarro LM, Martins IS. 2012.** Global biodiversity change: the bad, the good, and
622 the unknown. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* **37**(1), 25–50.
623 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-042911-093511>

624 **Perring MP, Diekmann M, Midolo G, Schellenberger Costa D, Bernhardt-Römermann M,**
625 **Otto JCJ, Gilliam FS, Hedwall P-O, Nordin A, Dirnböck T et al. 2018a.** Understanding
626 context dependency in the response of forest understorey plant communities to nitrogen

627 deposition. *Environmental Pollution* **242**, 1787–1799.
628 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.07.089>

629 **Perring MP, Bernhardt-Römermann M, Baeten L, Midolo G, Blondeel H, Depauw L,**
630 **Landuyt D, Maes SL, De Lombaerde E, Carón MM et al. 2018b.** Global environmental
631 change effects on plant community composition trajectories depend upon management
632 legacies. *Global Change Biology* **24**(4): 1722–1740. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14030>

633 **Pimm SL, Russell G, Gittleman JL, Brooks TM. 1995.** The future of biodiversity. *Science* **269**:
634 347–350. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.269.5222.347>

635 **Prach J, Kopecký M. 2018.** Landscape-scale vegetation homogenization in Central European
636 sub-montane forests over the past 50 years. *Applied Vegetation Science* **21**(3): 373-384.
637 <https://doi.org/10.1111/avsc.12372>

638 **Prausová R, Doležal J, Rejmánek M. 2020.** Nine decades of major compositional changes in a
639 Central European beech forest protected area. *Plant Ecology* **221**: 1005-1016.
640 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11258-020-01057-6>

641 **R Core Team. 2023.** *R: a language and environment for statistical computing, v.4.3.0.* Vienna,
642 Austria: R foundation for Statistical Computing. URL <http://www.r-project.org>.

643 **Rigling A, Bigler C, Eilmann B, Feldmeyer-Christe E, Gimmi U, Ginzler C, Graf U, Mayer P,**
644 **Vacchiano G, Weber P et al. 2013.** Driving factors of a vegetation shift from Scots pine to
645 pubescent oak in dry Alpine forests. *Global Change Biology* **19**(1): 229–240.
646 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12038>

647 **Rogers DA, Rooney TP, Olson D, Waller DM. 2008.** Shifts in southern Wisconsin forest
648 canopy and understory richness, composition, and heterogeneity. *Ecology* **89**(9): 2482–
649 2492.

650 **Roleček J, Vild O, Sladký J, Řepka R. 2017.** Habitat requirements of endangered species in a
651 former coppice of high conservation value. *Folia Geobotanica* **52**(1): 59–69.
652 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12224-016-9276-6>

653 **Roth M, Michiels H-G, Puhmann H, Sucker C, Winter M-B, Hauck M. 2021.** Responses of
654 temperate forests to nitrogen deposition: Testing the explanatory power of modeled
655 deposition datasets for vegetation gradients. *Ecosystems* **24**(5): 1222–1238.
656 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-020-00579-4>

657 **Roth M, Müller-Meißner A, Michiels H-G, Hauck M. 2022.** Vegetation changes in the
658 understory of nitrogen-sensitive temperate forests over the past 70 years. *Forest Ecology*
659 *and Management* **503**: 119754. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2021.119754>

660 **Szabó P, Hédl R, Šipoš J. 2021.** Standard trees versus underwood: Historical patterns of tree
661 taxon occurrence in coppice forests. *Journal of Vegetation Science* **32**(1): e12963.
662 <https://doi.org/10.1111/JVS.12963>

663 **Tape K, Sturm M, Racine C. 2006.** The evidence for shrub expansion in Northern Alaska and
664 the Pan-Arctic. *Global Change Biology* **12**(4): 686–702. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2006.01128.x)
665 [2486.2006.01128.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2006.01128.x)

666 **Tichý L. 2002.** JUICE, software for vegetation classification. *Journal of Vegetation Science* **13**:
667 451–453. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-1103.2002.tb02069.x>

- 668 **Tichý L. 2005.** New similarity indices for the assignment of relevés to the vegetation units of an
669 existing phytosociological classification. *Plant Ecology* **179**(1): 67–72.
670 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11258-004-5798-8>
- 671 **Tylianakis JM, Didham RK, Bascompte J, Wardle DA. 2008.** Global change and species
672 interactions in terrestrial ecosystems. *Ecology Letters* **11**(12): 1351-1363.
673 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2008.01250.x>
- 674 **Valdez JW, Callaghan CT, Junker J, Purvis A, Hill SL, Pereira HM. 2023.** The undetectability
675 of global biodiversity trends using local species richness. *Ecography* **2023**: e06604.
676 <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.06604>
- 677 **Van Calster H, Baeten L, Schrijver A De, Keersmaecker L De, Rogister JE, Verheyen K,**
678 **Hermy M. 2007.** Management driven changes (1967–2005) in soil acidity and the
679 understorey plant community following conversion of a coppice-with-standards forest.
680 *Forest Ecology and Management* **241**(1–3): 258–271.
681 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2007.01.007>
- 682 **Vandvik V, Skarpaas O, Klanderud K, Telford RJ, Halbritter AH. 2020.** Biotic rescaling
683 reveals importance of species interactions for variation in biodiversity responses to climate
684 change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **117**(37): 22858–22865.
685 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2003377117>
- 686 **Vellend M. 2017.** The biodiversity conservation paradox. *American Scientist* **105**(2): 94-101.
- 687 **Vellend M, Baeten L, Myers-Smith IH, Elmendorf SC, Beauséjour R, Brown CD, De Frenne**
688 **P, Verheyen K, Wipf S. 2013.** Global meta-analysis reveals no net change in local-scale
689 plant biodiversity over time. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the*
690 *United States of America* **110**(48): 19456–19459. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1312779110>

- 691 **Verheyen K, Baeten L, De Frenne P, Bernhardt-Römermann M, Brunet J, Cornelis J,**
692 **Decocq G, Dierschke H, Eriksson O, Hédli R et al. 2012.** Driving factors behind the
693 eutrophication signal in understorey plant communities of deciduous temperate forests.
694 *Journal of Ecology* **100**: 352–365. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.200421705>
- 695 **Verheyen K, Bažány M, Chečko E, Chudomelová M, Closset-Kopp D, Czortek P, Decocq**
696 **G, De Frenne P, De Keersmaecker L, Enríquez García C et al. 2018.** Observer and
697 relocation errors matter in resurveys of historical vegetation plots. *Journal of Vegetation*
698 *Science* **29**: 812–823. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jvs.12673>
- 699 **Wang WJ, He HS, Thompson FR, Fraser JS, Hanberry BB, Dijak WD. 2015.** Importance of
700 succession, harvest, and climate change in determining future composition in U.S. Central
701 Hardwood Forests. *Ecosphere* **6**(12): 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1890/ES15-00238.1>
- 702 **Westhoff V, van der Maarel E. 1978.** The Braun-Blanquet approach. In: Whittaker RH (ed.)
703 *Classification of plant communities*, W. Junk, The Hague, NL, 289-399.
- 704 **Zellweger F, De Frenne P, Lenoir J, Vangansbeke P, Verheyen K, Bernhardt-Römermann**
705 **M, Baeten L, Hédli R, Berki I, Brunet J et al. 2020.** Forest microclimate dynamics drive
706 plant responses to warming. *Science* **368**(6492): 772–775.
707 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba6880>
- 708 **Zlatník A. 1953.** *Fytocenologie lesa*. SPN, Prague, Czech Republic.